

ON

OSTEAL OR PERIOSTEAL CACHEXIA.

BY

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The following notes are more imperfect than they would have been could I have made them otherwise. Such as they are, they seem to relate to a kind of disease whereof the foremost characters are cachexia and swelling of bone.

With regard to the cachexia, it is to be especially noted that there were no reasons for connecting it with disease of the spleen, liver, or lymphatic glands, with leucocythæmia, or albuminuria. In two of the patients there was a slight hæmorrhagic tendency, common in cachexia.

With regard to the bone disease, the questions of rickets and of syphilis at once arise. And first as to rickets. Three of the patients were rickety, in respect of the beading of the ribs. But rickets alone begets not so deep a cachexia, unless associated with enlargement of the spleen. Nor is enlargement of bones, such as described in the notes, known to be a sign of rickets. The second case might almost be called *mollities ossium*: the others were more like periostitis.

Next as to syphilis. None of the patients showed any proof of syphilis, unless the state of the skull in the third case be so deemed. The possibility of syphilis we cannot deny; but this cachexy, if a form of syphilis, is a form hitherto unknown to me.

CASE I.

H., a baby, 14 months old; seen with Dr. Grosvenor of Notting Hill, on October 23, 1878. For two months the lower half of the right femur and the right tibia had been enlarging and painful. When I saw the child the enlargement of the

bones mentioned was considerable ; there were no signs of subperiosteal suppuration. The pallor was extreme. There was no fever. No signs of any internal disease, except of slight pulmonary catarrh. The next day the child died.

CASE II.

F. M., a male, aged 12 months, seen with Dr. Sheldon of Notting Hill, on November 30, 1878. Nothing noteworthy in his stock, unless it be that there have been several deaths from phthisis pulmonalis in his mother's family. He is the fifth child; the others are healthy. F. also was healthy until he was 7½ months old, when he began to pine, and to suffer from pains in his limbs. Soon afterwards the thigh and other bones began to enlarge. Now there is a deep cachexia; no heat of skin; great sweats about head; great tenderness of body. Liver and spleen seem natural; no physical signs of disease of any of the organs of the chest or belly. A small lump, the bigness of a cherry stone, showing dark through the skin, in the lower dorsal region, and a little to the right of the spine, has been seen for two weeks. Great enlargement of the femora, scapulæ, heads of humeri, carpal ends of radii. Very weak in the back. During each inspiration the chest becomes thus deformed—the whole front sinks inwards between two lines drawn perpendicularly through the anterior axillary folds, so that on a horizontal section the chest would be kidney-shaped. The ribs bend in the bone much outside the costo-chondral joint; the deformity is quite unlike that of rickets; the sternum recedes. The ends of the ribs are not much enlarged; the anterior fontanelle is nearly closed: he has six teeth. He died December 7, 1878, "without any other marked symptoms than when we saw him" (Dr. Sheldon).

CASE III.

M., a girl, 12 months old; seen May 19, 1879. She is the fourth child; there have been no miscarriages or stillborn children. She is moderately rickety, judging by the beading of the ribs. The lower end of both tibiæ is much swollen for two inches upwards; tender also, so as to suggest periostitis: has been so for two months. There are no undoubted signs of inherited syphilis about the child; and the father denies having suffered from chancres, but he owns to gonorrhœa.

June 10.—The tibiæ as before; the lower half of the right femur and both shoulders are much swollen. The skull is not natiform, but there are marked nodes on the os frontis at each

side of the fontanelle, just as described by Parrot. Deep cachexia; hæmorrhage into the left eyelid, and into the gums where the teeth are being cut; a bruise over the sternum. The spleen is impalpable. There is no leucocytosis. The child's vaccination wounds did not heal well, and have left large scars, unlike those of ordinary vaccinia. Dr. Cree, of Highgate, who vaccinated the child, tells me that "the vaccine matter he used was from quite a healthy child, one of my own patients, whom I had vaccinated with the calf lymph from Belgium, which I occasionally use. So that no syphilis could have been introduced from that quarter."

July 24.—The child seems much the same, the swellings no less, and the cachexia as great. She died two or three months afterwards.

CASE IV.

S., a girl, 16 months old; seen May 19, 1879. The fifth child which was born alive; the first and fourth are dead; between the third and fourth came a miscarriage, also between the fourth and fifth. The child is much emaciated; the ribs show signs of considerable rickets. There are no signs of inherited syphilis; the skull has not the characters described by Parrot. The lower end of the right tibia was swollen and tender. The child was not seen again.

CASE V.

R., a boy, aged 9 months; seen on September 9, 1880, with Dr. Glover, of Highbury. He was brought up by hand. He had never been a healthy child; had bad eczema once, leaving a few scars. There were no reasons for suspecting inherited syphilis. About six weeks ago he had what was at first thought to be dropsy of the left leg. For the last few weeks the urine has been bloody; Dr. Glover deemed it to be chiefly a hæmatinuria. Great cachexia; no fever; liver and spleen impalpable. Urine slightly blood-tinged; a minute trace of albumen. No reason for suspecting stone; nothing amiss to be felt in abdomen. Lower half of left tibia much enlarged, probably very painful, especially at night. Lower end of right radius enlarged. Ribs much beaded. Has cut the two middle lower incisors. Heart and lungs natural. We ordered him to take cod-liver oil and iodide of potassium. On October 8 Dr. Glover wrote as follows:—"Our little patient is very much better, and presents a very different appearance from what you saw. He is quite lively, and sits up in the nurse's arms; bears handling about the ribs, or

about the leg. The anæmia and œdema are gone. The swelling of the leg too has almost disappeared, with the tenderness. The urine is no longer smoky. There seems every prospect of his doing well. The iodide did not seem to suit him or do him good, so I put him on Parrish's syrup, and it is under that that the improvement has set in."

SAINT
BARTHOLOMEW'S HOSPITAL
REPORTS.

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AND

JOHN LANGTON, F.R.C.S.

VOL. XVII.

LONDON:

SMITH, ELDER, & CO., 15 WATERLOO PLACE.

1881.

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